

Backward castes movement and Political Participation in Andhra Pradesh

Dr. M. Akshutha Nandh
Lecturer in Political Science,
SVGM.Government Degree College
Kalyandurg

ABSTRACT

The concept of political representation and how the caste has taken a new form and is helping the traditional caste groups get politically mobilized and take active politics in the Democratic politics of the nation is thoroughly analyzed along with the various social movements that are related to caste system in different parts of the country. Similarly, the objective of the study, the hypotheses along with the methodology, Sample Design, Need of the study, Scope of the study, that is adopted for the sake of this study. Social Stratification is a ubiquitous social system in human societies, be it simple or complex. Stratification is fairly permanent ranking of positions in a society in terms of unequal power, prestige or privileges. It refers to the patterned or structured social inequalities among the whole categories people not just among individuals. The Caste system is the unique dimension, on which the Indian society is stratified into higher and lower castes with differential access to resources of society. The heredity occupations have created vested interests in the form of sociolect-economic monopolies and have bred an extreme form of exploitation. The main attribute of caste system is ritualistic purity, and this in turn has created inflexibility, rigidity and feelings of superiority and inferiority. Some scholars hold the view that, caste is a particularly a rigid form of class and think its existence to be worldwide. Others believe it persists only in India and is peculiar to. Thus the Indian political system cannot be said to be non respective to the emergence and dominance of Backward Castes leaders even though the political representation of Backward Castes has not particularly registered a significant increase over the last 16 general elections. While on the one hand most Backward Castes politicians have found it difficult to rise within upper castes dominated party hierarchies, on the other hand some Backward Castes have managed to become leaders when they have set up parties of their own. Once they have established themselves as leaders, there has been an unquestioning acceptance of their leadership and decisions by the party rank and file, even if it is largely upper caste.

KEYWORDS: Social Stratification, Democratic Politics, Indian Society, Caste system, Upper Caste, Backward castes Leadership.

Backward Castes.Caste System

In India, caste is the most important basis of social categorization. Initially caste originated on the basis of division of people on the basis of their natural inclinations and occupations and over a period of time it has turned out to be hereditary. It has created social groups based on kinship and ethnicity. The heredity occupations have created vested interests in the form of socio-economic monopolies and have bred an extreme form of exploitation. The main attribute of caste system is ritualistic purity, and this in turn has created inflexibility, rigidity and feelings of superiority and inferiority.

Basing on different perspectives there are various definitions of caste. How does one define caste? Although many social scientists have done epoch- making work on the Indian caste system, no two social scientists concur on its definition. They also differ on the meaning of caste. Some scholars hold the view that, caste is a particularly a rigid form of class and think its existence to be worldwide. Others believe it persists only in India and is peculiar to.

On the other hand, G.S.Ghurye, says that caste is strictly limited to the Hindus. He gives six outstanding features of the caste system: (1) segmental division of society (2) hierarchy (3) restrictions of feeling and social intercourse (4) civil and religious disparities and privileges of different sections (5) lack of unrestricted choice of occupation and (6) restrictions on marriage. He further says that the caste system is one of the oldest and the most elaborate systems of social organization. The position of an individual in the ritually determined hierarchy defines the entire course of his life.

The British historian H.H.Risley (1969) propounds a racist theory of caste. He argued that there were basic racial and physical differences among the various castes. This theory traces the origin of the caste system to the Aryan Invasion of India and links it to the process by which the invaders could subordinate the indigenous inhabitants and integrate them as peasants and slaves within a stratified society. This theory fails to explain the taboo on food and marriage. This view has been rejected by Indian intellectuals and politicians, including B.R.Ambedkar. Social reformers like Jyothirao phule and the leaders of the non-Brahmin movement in Tamil Nadlu also reject the Aryan theory, in which social superiority has been given to the Brahmin.

M.N.Srinivas, considers caste, as a cultural phenomenon. He refers to four features of caste (Brahmin, Kshatriya, Vysya, Sudhra) as embodied in Varna.

In one sense, all the castes which were considered upper in hierarchy in pre-British India were mainly urban and were sources of ritual and secular power or were close to these sources. Because of these initial advantages of higher status, the people belonging to these castes were the first to exploit the modern economic and educational opportunities that opened up during British rule, which the vast majority of the populace, who were mainly rural were deprived of these benefits. The latter remained backward in the traditional social order.

The Backward classes of contemporary India had their origin from the numerous artisan castes that were part of the societal schema of stratification, in which these castes were only just above the so called untouchables and their duty was to render services to the three higher castes in tune with the duties that were assigned to them as envisaged in the four Varna system.

The artisan castes though considered as backward were not treated as polluting as the untouchables because of their functional necessity for the agrarian society. They were allowed to reside in the vicinity of the village and their entry into the household was permitted when needed. But, both the Scheduled Castes and the Backward castes were socially set apart, excluded from power, education and rituals. In a nut shell, they were socially excluded, though they were rendering different essential services for the society.

J.H.Hutton as per a survey conducted during the British era came to a conclusion that there were about 3,000 castes existing in the country with relative degree of purity and pollution which were devoid of social, economic and political power and remained outside the social orbit and their efforts to attain social mobility was dissuaded and strongly discouraged by the higher castes.

On this basis, The Government of India gave a Commission Name by Mandal Commission; the Mandal Commission in the last decade of 20th century, identified 3743 castes to form India's other Backward classes, representing 52% of the country's population. Observing that the OBCs occupied only 12.5% of civil service posts, it recommended a 27% reservation for them in those posts. This figure was not proportional to their population. However, to be spared the ire of the judges, who, since the apex court upheld the decision, were concerned with keeping quota totals below 50% (these 27% in fact were in addition to the 15% in favour of the Scheduled Castes and the 7.5% in favour of the Scheduled Tribes) recommended that figure.

POLITICAL REPRESENTATION

The concept of political representation is misleadingly simple: everyone seems to know what it is, yet few can agree on any particular definition. In fact, there is an extensive literature that offers many different definitions of this elusive concept. Hanna Pitkin provides, perhaps, one of the most straightforward definitions: to represent is simply to "make present again." As per this definition, political representation is nothing but making citizens' voices, opinions, and perspectives "present" in the public policy making processes.¹¹ When political representatives not only speak but also advocate and champion the cause of the people, both symbolize and act on behalf of the vast majority of people in the political arena, political representation then occurs. In essence, political representation refers to kind of political assistance that the political representatives give to the people at large. This seemingly straightforward definition, however, is squarely not sufficient and inadequate because it leaves the concept of political representation underspecified and does not convey the full meaning of the term.¹²

Andrew Rehfeld has come out with a general theory of representation where he simply identifies representation by referring to a group of relevant audience who accept a person as their representative. One significant but pernicious consequence of this approach to representation is that it allows both democratic as well as undemocratic cases of representation. Another draw back with this theory of representation is that it does not state in unambiguous terms as to what a representative should do or should not do in order to be recognized as a representative. And what exactly representatives *do* has been a hotly contested and debated issue. In particular, a controversy has always persisted as to whether the representatives should act as *delegates* or *trustees*.¹³

TYPES OF REPRESENTATION

In a Representative Democracy, elections, on the basis of universal adult Franchise, are usually held. It connotes that each man or woman, without any discrimination on grounds of gender, caste, creed, region, language, culture etc, after attaining a certain prescribed age (such as 18 years or 21 years) is entitled to vote in the elections. All voters of a community who are entitled to participate in elections are collectively described as the electorate. Next comes the question as to on what basis should the representatives be elected by the electorate. The answer to this question leads to two alternative systems of representation. They are:

(A) Territorial representation (B) Functional Representation

THEORIES OF REPRESENTATION

The role of the representatives of the people in the process of policy-making is again a contentious issue. While some argue that they should be authorized to control the entire process; there are others who opine that they should perform a limited function on behalf of the people they represent. There are different theories of representation expressing different shades of opinion. They are as follows:

A) **Reactionary Theory of Representation.**

B) **Conservative theory of Representation.**

C) **Liberal Theory of Representation.**

D) **Radical Theory of representation.**

BACKWARD CLASSES POULATION IN ANDHRA PRADESH

The Government of Andhra Pradesh, in April 1968, appointed the Anantharaman Commission with an intention to determine the criteria of backwardness and also to prepare a list of backward classes in Andhra Pradesh. The report was submitted by the Commission in June, 1970. Basing on the report of the Commission, 92 classes were officially listed as socially and educationally backward and these backward castes were later classified into 4 groups viz. A,B,C&D and the Report further recommended 30% for OBCs. The Government of Andhra Pradesh, however, fixed the quota as 29% in educational Institutions and also in Government services. The backward classes which are given 29% of reservation is classified as follows: BC-A-7%; BC-B-10%; BC-C-1%; BC-D-7%; Now, recently some sections of the Muslims were categorised as another backward class group and they were enlisted under another group, namely BC-E- 4% (Some Sects of Muslims).

In a fresh twist to the controversy over the proportion of OBCs to the overall population in India, a government survey which was released on September 1, 2007 indicated that the Backward Castes formed about 41% of the total populace. The OBC population in the country, according to a survey by the National Sample Survey Organisation (NSSO) put it at 40.94%, while the population of SCs was put at 19.59%, and that of STs was put at 8.63% and the rest was put at 30.80%. The number is not really of great significance statistically because the NSSO survey was basically aimed at measuring the level of consumption expenditure by different households and not estimating the population of OBCs, SCs and STs. In fact, a similar survey done in 1999-2000 had put the OBC population at about 35% and it is hardly likely that the proportion has gone up by 6% in just five years - the latest survey was done in 2004-05.

Back ward Castes movement in Andhra Pradesh

The role played by the modern historical consciousness of region and language in the writing of caste historiography during the first half of the twentieth century has contributed to the creation of caste consciousness. It studies the Telugu-speaking Kammas, a dominant caste in Andhra, a region that has witnessed a vehement movement for linguistic states. Ever since the chaotic disputes on Andhra historiography flared up in 1910, ways to interpret the regional past have become crucial for their self-definition in the newly acquired idea of India as well as that of Hinduism with the whole debate ultimately leading to the emergence of some influential historiographies on the Kamma caste. Different historiographies from those of non-Brahmin leaders, Suriyadevara Raghavayya Chaudari and Tripuraneni Ramswami Chaudari, to the socialist cum nationalist

leader, N.G. Ranga, and a caste movement ideologue, Kotta Bhavayya Chaudari demonstrates the correlation and complicity between history and caste identity and homeland language movements. They were, in a sense, on the lookout for a new, totally different history.

The role of caste become a preponderant thing in Andhra Pradesh because the state happens to be a highly caste conscious one. After the emergence of non-Brahmin movement with its own separate identity, two sub-castes, namely, the Reddys and Kammas began to play a more conscious and prominent role in Andhra Pradesh politics. Andhra Pradesh is one of the states where non- Brahmin Movement has changed the sphere of politics. Geographically, it has three regions, namely, Coastal Andhra, Telangana and Rayalaseema. The state of Andhra Pradesh though is backward economically, yet has contributed many political leaders for independence movement.

Table – 1
Backward Caste Representatives Elected For Lok Sabha
Andhra Pradesh from 1952 to 2014

Year	Name	Constituency	Caste	Party affiliation
1952	B.Rajagopala Rao	Srikakulam	Kalinga	INDT
1957	K.Ashanna	Adilabad	Munnurukapu	INC
	B.Rajagopala Rao	Srikakulam	Kalinga	INC
1962	B. Rajagopala Rao	Srikakulam	Kalinga	INC
1967	Karri Narayana Rao	Bobbili	Turupukapu	INC
	Sangem . Laxmi	Medak	Yadav	INC
	Gouthu Lachanna	Srikakulam	Srishayana	INDT
1971	S.R.A.S. Appalanayudu	Anakapalli	Gavara	INC
	Karri Narayana Rao	Bobbili	Turpukapu	INC
	Mallikarjuna	Medak	Gouda	INC
	B.Rajagopala Rao	Srikakulam	Kalinga	INC
	S.B. Giri	Warangal	Meru	INC
1977	S.R.A.S.Appala Nayudu	Anakapalli	Gavara	INC
	K.S Narayana	Hyderabad	Mudiraj	INC
	Mallikarjun	Medak	Gouda	INC
	B. Rajagopala Rao	Srikakulam	Kalinga	INC
	Gode Murahari	Vijayawada	Perika	INC
	G. Mallikarjuna Rao	Warngal	Gouda	INC
1980	S.R.A.S. Appala Nayudu	Anakapalli	Gavara	INC
	K.S. Narayana	Hyderabad	Mudiraj	INC
	Mallikarjun	Mahaboobnagar	Goud	INC
	P. Shiva Shankar	Secunderabad	Munurukapu	INC
	B. Rajagopala Rao	Srikakulam	Kalinga	INC
1984	P. Appala Narsimham	Anakapalli	Gavara	TDP
	Chimata Saambu	Bapatla	Yadav	TDP
	T. Bala Goud	Nizamabad	Goud	INC
	H. Ayyappa Dora	Srikakulam	Gavara	TDP
1989	Konatala. Ramakrishna	Anakapalli	Gavara	INC
	S. Gangadhar	Hindupur	Valimiki	INC
	Mallikarjun	MahaboobNagar	Gouda	INC
	T. Bala Gouda	Nizamabad	Gouda	INC

	Kanti. Vishwanatham	Srikakulam	Kalinga	INC
1991	K. Ramakrishna	Anakapalli	Gavara	INC
	S. Gangadhar	Hindupur	Valmiki	INC
	Kolusu Pedda Reddaiah	Machilpatnam	Yadava	TDP
	Mallikarjun	Mahaboobnagar	Gouda	INC
	Bommagani. Dharmabiksham	Nalgonda	Gouda	CPI
	K. Vishwanatham	Srikakulam	Kalinga	INC
	Bandaru Dattatreya	Secunderabad	Kuruma	TDP
1996	C.H.Ayyanna paatrudu	Anakapalli	Koppula velama	TDP
	S. Ramachandra Reddy	Hindhupur	Golla	TDP
	L. Ramana	Karim Nagar	Padma Sali	TDP
	Malli karjuna	Mahaboob Nagar	Gouda	INC
	Bommagani Dharmabiksham	Nalgonda	Gouda	CPI
	Kinjarapu Yerrannayudu	Srikakulam	Polinati Velama	TDP
	K. Paiditalli Naidu	Vijayanagaram	Koppula Velama	TDP
1998	S. Gangadhar	Hindhupur	Valmiki	INC
	Bandaru Dattatreya	Secundrabad	Kurama	BJP
	K.Yerrannadu	Srikakulam	Polinati Velma	TDP
	K. Paiditalli Naidu	Vijayanagaram	Koppula Velama	TDP
1999	Kaluva Srinivasulu	Ananthapur	Valmiki	TDP
	B.K. Parthasarathi	Hindupur	Kuruba	TDP
	K.E. Krishna Murthy	Kurnool	Ediga	TDP
	A. Narendra	Medak	Padmasali	BJP
	Bandaru Dattatreya	Secundrabad	Kurama	BJP
	K.Yerrannadu	Srikakulam	Polinati Velma	TDP
	Botcha Sathyanarayana	ViZayanagaram	Turupu kapu	INC
	Bodakunti Venkateswarlu	Warangal	Perika	TDP
2004	D. Vittal Rao	Mahaboob nagar	Padmasali	INC
	A.Narendra	Medak	Padmasali	TRS
	Madhu yashki goud	Nizamabad	Gouda	INC
	Anjankumar Yadav	Secundrabad	Yadav	INC
	K.Yerrannadu	Srikakulam	Polinati Velma	TDP
	Smt. Botcha Janshi	Vizayanagaram	Turupu kapu	INC
	K. Paiditalli Naidu	Vijayanagaram	Koppula Velama	TDP
2009	Sabbam Hari	Anakapalli	Koppula Velama	INC
	Nimmala Kistappa	Hindupur	Devanga	TDP
	Ponnam Prabhakar	Karimnagar	Gouda	INC
	Narayana Rao.K	Machilipatnam	Gouda	TDP
	Madhu Yashki Goud	Nizamabad	Gouda	INC
	Anjankumar Yadav	Secundrabad	Yadav	INC
	Smt. Killi Krupa Rani	Srikakulam	Kalinga	INC
	Smt. Botcha Janshi	Vizayanagaram	Turupu kapu	INC
2014	Nimmala Kistappa	Hindupur	Devanga	TDP
	Butta Renuka	Kurnool	Boya	YSRCP
	Konakalla Naryana Rao	Machilipatnam	Gouda	TDP
	Rammohan Naidu Kinjarapu	Srikaakula	Polanati Velama	TDP
	Sri Bandaru Dattatreya	Secuendra Bad	Kuraba	BJP
	Sri. Dr. Boora Gouda	Nalgonda	Gouda	TRS

Source: Election Commission of India

Table 1 gives us information about the list of Backward Class Members of Parliament elected to the Lok Sabha from 1952 to 2014. In the year 1952, one Member of Parliament was elected from Srikakulam as an independent Member of Parliament. In the year 1957, two members of Parliament were elected as representatives of Indian National Congress. In 1962, one backward class Member of Parliament was elected to the Lok Sabha on the ticket of Indian National Congress. In 1967, three backward class leaders were elected to the Lok Sabha from Andhra Pradesh. Among them two were from Indian National Congress and one was an independent candidate. In the year 1971, Andhra Pradesh sent 5 backward class representatives to the Lok Sabha and all the 5 representatives represented Indian National Congress. In the year 1977, there were six backward class representatives from Andhra Pradesh in the Lok Sabha and all the six representatives represented Indian national Congress. In the year 1980, there were five backward class Members of Parliament in the Lok Sabha and all the five representatives were from Indian National Congress. In the year 1984, there were four backward class Members of Parliament in the Lok Sabha and among them three were from Telugu Desam party and one was from Indian national Congress. In 1989, there were five backward class leaders representing Andhra Pradesh in Lok Sabha and all the five representatives were from Indian National Congress. In the year 1991, there were seven backward class representatives in Lok Sabha from Andhra Pradesh and among them four were from Indian National Congress two were from Telugu Desam Party and one was from Communist Party of India. In the year 1996, there were eight backward class representatives from Andhra Pradesh in Lok Sabha. Among them six represented the Telugu Desam party and one represented Indian National Congress and one was from Communist Party of India. In the year 1998, there were four backward class representatives from Andhra Pradesh in Lok Sabha. Two were from the Telugu Desam Party one was from Bharatiya Janata Party, and one was from Indian National Congress. In the year 1999, there were eight backward class representatives from Andhra Pradesh in Lok Sabha. Among them five are from the Telugu Desam Party, two from Bharatiya Janata Party, and one from Indian National Congress. In the year 2004, there were seven backward class representatives from Andhra Pradesh in Lok Sabha and among them four were from Indian National Congress and two from the Telugu Desam Party and one from TRS. In the year 2009, there were eight backward class representatives from Andhra Pradesh in the Lok Sabha and among them six were from Indian National Congress and two were from the Telugu Desam Party. In the year 2014, there were Six backward castes representatives From both states in the Lok Sabha and among them three were from Telugu Desam Party, one were from YSRCP, one were from TRS, and one were from BJP.

Table – 2

Backward Caste Representatives from 1953 to 2014 in A.P.**State Legislative Assembly**

S.No.		Year	No. of Back ward caste Representatives
I.	Andhra State Legislative Assembly	1953	24
I.	A.P. State Assembly	1956	Na
II.	A.P. State Assembly	1957	28
III.	A.P. State Assembly	1962	38
IV.	A.P. State Assembly	1967	46
V.	A.P. State Assembly	1972	52
VI.	A.P. State Assembly	1978	55
VII.	A.P. State Assembly	1983	47
VIII.	A.P. State Assembly	1985	50
IX	A.P. State Assembly	1989	45
X	A.P. State Assembly	1994	59
XI	A.P. State Assembly	1999	57
XII	A.P. State Assembly	2004	52
XIII	A.P. State Assembly	2009	55
XIV	A.P. State Assembly	2014	27(AP)+33(TG)

Source: Election Commission of India⁴⁶.

The table 2 gives us information about the number of Backward Castes representatives in Andhra Pradesh State legislature. In the year 1953, out of 300 representatives in Andhra Pradesh state legislature, 24 represented from backward castes. In the State Legislative Assembly elections conducted in 1957, 28 backward class leaders were elected to the Andhra Pradesh State legislature. In the 1962 elections conducted for the Andhra Pradesh State legislature, 38 people were represented from backward class. In the year 1967, 46 backward class representatives were elected to the Andhra Pradesh State Legislative Assembly. In the elections conducted in 1972 to the Andhra Pradesh State Legislative Assembly, 52 backward class leaders were elected to the Assembly. In 1978 elections were held to the Andhra Pradesh State Legislative Assembly, 55 backward class leaders were elected. In 1983 elections were held to the Andhra Pradesh State Legislative Assembly, 47 backward classe representing were elected to the Assembly. In the year 1985, when the elections were conducted to the Andhra Pradesh State Legislative Assembly, 50 people were representing from backward classes. In 1989 elections conducted to the Andhra Pradesh State Legislative Assembly, 45 representing backward classes Leaders were elected to the Assembly. In the 1994 elections conducted to the Andhra Pradesh State Legislative Assembly, 59 backward class leaders were sent to Assembly. In the 1999 elections conducted in Andhra Pradesh State legislature, 57 people representing the backward classes were elected. In the 2004 elections conducted to the Andhra Pradesh State Legislative Assembly, 52 representing backward classes were sent to the state assembly. In the year 2009, when the elections are conducted to the Andhra Pradesh State legislature, 55 representing backward classes were elected. In the year 2014, the State of Andhra Pradesh was bifurcated into Telangana and Andhra Pradesh. In the residuary state of Andhra Pradesh, in elections conducted

in 2014 there were 27 representatives representing the backward classes. In the State of Telangana, there were 33 representatives representing the backward classes.

Table - 3

District Level Elected Backward Castes Representatives of Andhra Pradesh in Zilla Parishad Local Body Elections 2001, 2006 and 2014

Elected as	Total in 2001	B.C	Total in 2006	B.C	Total in 2014	B.C
a. ZP Chairpersons	22	07	22	08	22	07
b. ZP Vice Chairpersons	22	05	22	09	22	08
c. ZPTC Members	1,098	366	1,098	347	1,098	363

Source: Election Commission of A.P State

The Table 3 throws light on the backward caste representatives elected to the local body elections (Zilla Parishads) in the years 2001, 2006 and 2014. In the 2001 elections conducted to the Zilla Parishads, out of 22 Zilla Parishads Chairpersons, seven chairpersons were from backward castes. Likewise, out of 22 Zilla Parishads' Vice- chairpersons, 5 were from backward castes. Out of 1098 ZPTC Members 366 belonged to the backward castes.

Similarly, in the year 2006, elections were conducted to the Zilla Parishads. Out of 22 Zilla Parishad Chairpersons, eight persons were from backward castes and out of 22 Zilla Parishads Vice-chairpersons, 9 were from backward castes. Out of 1098 ZPTC Members, 347 were from backward castes. In the year 2014, elections were conducted to the Zilla Parishads. Out of 22 Zilla Parishad Chairperson posts, 7 were occupied by the backward castes and similarly out of 22 zilla Parishad Vice-chairperson posts, eight posts were occupied by the backward castes.. And out of 1098 ZPTC members, 363 belong to the backward castes

Table - 4

Mandal Level Elected Backward Castes Representatives of Andhra Pradesh in Mandal Parishad Local Body Elections 2001, 2006 and 2014

Elected as	Total in 2001	B.C	Total in 2006	B.C	Total in 2014	B.C
a. M.P.Ps	1,098	371	1,098	431	1,098	347
b. MPTCs	16,589	5918	16,589	6437	16,148	6095

Source: Election Commission of A.P State

The Table 4 depicts the backward castes representation in the Mandal Parishads. In the year 2001, elections were conducted to the Mandal Parishads. Out of 1098 Mandal Presidents, 371 representatives were from backward castes. In the 2006 elections conducted to the Mandal Parishads, out of 1098 Mandal Presidents, 431 belong to the backward castes. Similarly, out of 16589 MPTCs, 6437 belong to the backward castes. In the year 2014, elections were conducted to the Mandal Parishads. Out of 1098 Mandal President posts, 347 were occupied by people belonging to backward class. Similarly, out of 16, 148 posts of MPTCs,

6095 were occupied by the people belonging to the backward castes.

Table - 5

Village Level Elected Backward Caste Representatives of Andhra Pradesh in Local Body Village Panchayats Elections 2006 and 2014.

District Level

Elected as	Total in 2006	B.C	Total in 2014	B.C
a. Village Sarpanches	21,469	10911	21,649	11524
b. Ward Members	2,17,789	137276	2,18,208	146524

Source: Election Commission of A.P State

The Table 5 depicts the Backward Castes representation in the Village Panchayats. In the local body elections held in 2006, out of 21, 469 village Sarpanches 10911 were from backward classes. Likewise, in the local body elections held in 2014, out of 21, 649 village sarpanches who are elected, 11524 belonged to backward classes. Out of 2, 17, 789 Ward members who were elected in the local body elections of 2006, 13 72 76 were from backward classes. Likewise, in the local body elections conducted in 2014, out of 2,18, 208, 146 524 were from the backward classes.

Objectives of the Study

Keeping the study gaps in the earlier studies and need for the study in mind, the following issues are considered as main objectives of the study. To analyse the concept of the Backward Castes system and the Politics of Backward Caste from historical perspectives and theories of representations for understanding the political participation and the representation patterns.

Methodology

The present study is based on both primary and secondary sources keeping in view the objectives of the research study. The primary data was collecting through the records. Most of the information is secured through administering. The secondary data is collected from the Gazettee records of Government of India and A.P, Reports of various studies and also from various books and journals pertaining to Backward Castes representation. Data is also collected from various national and regional news papers.

Hypothesis

1. There has been growing political awareness among the backward castes.

Scope of the Study

An attempt is made in this thesis to study the concept of Backward Castes rises and Political Participation in A.P

Need and Importance of study

selected for the purpose of studying the Back ward Caste political leadership. it is interesting to study the position and participation belonging to Backward Castes in the A.P politics. The Backward Caste population in the India, with its 46.1% share in the population largely resembles that of india 's Backward Caste population. Thus, it does not differ very much from the India in respect of demographic figures and the selection is very

much relevant for the same appearance as the caste composition and population.

Analysis of data

In the present study various statistical methods and tools such as comparative percentage, diagrams used to analyse the available data.

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10. The scheme of reservation is as follows: (1) Non-Brahmin Hindus: 42%; (2) Brahmins: 17%; (3) Muslims: 17%; (4) Anglo-Indians: 17%; (5) Depressed Classes: 8% (total 100%).
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